

Paper 5

Employee Engagement for Attrition Management

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Abstract

As economies develop and there is more choice of employment, Company will find it increasingly challenging to attract and retain talent and potential. This change in economic conditions would mean being less dependent on manufacturing markets and more focused on service industries. In the best of worlds, employees would love their jobs, like their fellow workers, work hard for their management, get paid well for their work done, have massive chances for advancement, and flexible schedules so they could attend to personal or family needs when essential. Employee engagement is an important tool in managing human capital.

Introduction:

A study stated that one of the most critical challenges now a days international firms are facing is attrition of good employees. The existing studies shows the different aspects of employee engagement and retention.

The studies concerned with employee engagement reveals that factors like level of employee engagement in highly correlated the nature of job, communication ease, leadership styles, trust level and job autonomy, level of motivation, work involvement, support from organization, performance appraisal, quality of work life, level of involvement in decision making, opportunity to grow are the strongest drivers of employee's engagement. The various studies on employee retention highlighted the following aspects like level of training & development facilities, culture of organization, leadership quality, feedbacks, compensation structures etc... Employee retention & engagement strategies to engage and retain talented workforce for longer period of time and also to improve the company standard.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the factors influencing employee satisfaction among employees in the company.
2. To develop an employee engagement programme for the organization.
3. To analyse the factors which can affect the level of retention & engagement of employees.

Methodology:

secondary source of information is by way of

- Reports
- Diaries
- Letters
- Books
- website

- Magazines and journals

About the study

A reduction in the number of employees through retirement, resignation or death is known as Attrition. Attrition is also called total turnover or wastage rate. Attrition is the function of demand and supply. The organization has continuous demand of experienced employees and globalization has created the need of fresh talent for getting new ideas. The demand comes from the growth of the industry and the policy of the company. These two main things decide whether there is a demand of fresher or experienced employees for the company.

IMPORTANCE OF STUDYING ATTRITION:

Attrition rate is increasing day by day and its especially the software industry which is affected the most. Why an Employee leaves a company is the question asked by most of the employers. Companies even hire Private HR professionals to study the company's work and find out why an employee is dissatisfied. HR department does the recruiting of new employees and then send them for training so that they can understand work and work culture and become better professionals. Each and every company faces employee turn over problem whether organisation is big or small. An employee leaves his present job for another job to get better pay package and good working conditions. Every Company calculates Employee attrition rate and takes measures to reduce it. The facts and figures are not made public as it may affect the image of the company in front of its own employees and its loyal customers.

various reasons for Employee Attrition -

- 1) Higher Pay Package in another company.
- 2). Good working Conditions.
- 3) Opportunities for growth in new company
- 4) Change of Place.
- 5) A better Boss in new company.
- 6) Brand Image of new company.

Employee attrition costs a lot to the company. There are various costs which are borne by the company at the start when the employee is under training period.

Costs such as:

- 1) Conveyance Cost.
- 2) Cost of lodging of the new employee.
- 3) Trainers cost.
- 4) Cost of venue where training will be conducted.
- 5) Materials to be supplied during training process.

A company has a training period of 3 to 6 months. During this time an employee is not fruitful for the company. If an employee leaves the company when he starts working, company suffers a big loss in terms of money as well as workforce. Every company takes measures to hold the talented workforce by means of perks, Increments, Bonus and extra facilities. No one wants to lose good brains to their competitors.

Now the question is how to reduce employee attrition. Following are the methods to reduce

employee attrition:

- ✓ Flexible working conditions have been given to employees who have problem working for more hours.
- ✓ Private hospitals for employees where they can get their regular health check-up done without spending much money.
- ✓ Free overseas tour once in a year when a target is achieved.
- ✓ Target for completion of a work should be there but that should not hamper an employee's personal life.
- ✓ Companies should conduct various seminars on how to balance personal and professional life. An employee can be productive if and only if his personal life is balanced. Make employees a part of your work culture family and see the difference.

WHY EMPLOYEES LEAVE THE ORGANIZATION?

Most employees leave their work for reasons other than money -and an organization can correct these reasons. Most leaving employees seek opportunities that allow them to use and develop their skills. Leaving employees want more meaning in their work ... they often indicate that they want to use their qualities and skills in challenging team work led by capable leaders.

- ✓ Hourly employees notice whether they are treated with respect, have capable management and interesting work.
- ✓ Clerical employees voice concerns such as "type of work," "use of skills and abilities" and "opportunities to learn"
- ✓ Professional employees cite concerns about "supervisory coaching and counseling," "company direction" and interesting work
- ✓ Managerial staff cite "career growth" and "leadership" as the major factors that influence their decisions to stay or leave, together with "opportunities for management" "ability of top management" "use of skills and abilities" and "work/family balance"

STRATEGIES TO MINIMIZE EMPLOYEE TURNOVER :

Strategies on how to minimize employee turnover like changing (or improving existing) policies towards recruitment, selection, induction, training, job design and wage payment. Policy choice, however, must be appropriate to the precise diagnosis of the problem. Employee turnover attributable to poor selection procedures. Employee turnover attributable to wage rates which produce earnings that are not competitive with other firms in the local labor market is unlikely to decrease were the policy adjustment merely to enhance the organization's provision of on-the-job training opportunities. Given that there is increase indirect and indirect costs of labour turnover, therefore, management are frequently exhorted to identify the reasons why people leave organization's so that appropriate action is taken by the management. Extensive research has shown that the following categories of human capital management factors provides a core set of measures that senior management can use to increase the effectiveness of their investment in people and improve overall corporate performance of business. Employee engagement, the organization's capacity to engage, retain, and optimize the value of its employees hinges on how

well jobs are designed, how employees' time is used, and the commitment and support that is shown to employees by the management would motivate employees to stay in organizations. Knowledge accessibility, the extent of the organization's collaborativeness and its capacity for making knowledge and ideas widely available to employees, would make employees to stay in the organization. Sharing of information should be made at all levels of management.

Suggestions:

After the analysis of various studies on employee retention & engagement some points might be considered for retention & engagement of employees as under:

- Actively promote organizational effectiveness, reputation and values & ethics
- Clear paths to advancements
- Ongoing Training & Education
- Offer the Right Benefits

Conclusion:

Employee satisfaction is a main asset to employee's engagement. Engaged employees are ready to perform various kinds of activities and also, they do exceptionally well in their job. The study highlighted the most influencing factors of employee satisfaction in the organization. A design for an employee engagement has been proposed to the management to enhance employee commitment. A study concluded that HRM practices like effective leadership, communication, value profiles must be integrated with strategic goal to achieve good financial condition of employee which leads to retention of employees.
